

ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION OF GLASS FIBERS IN POLYURETHANE MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The influence of environmental factors on the performance of a unidirectional fiberglass reinforced polyurethane composite has been investigated and the effect of water temperature, exposure time, and bending stress on the corrosion susceptibility of the fiberglass composite has been determined. The environments included salt water, distilled water, and ultraviolet/water vapor condensation. The reinforcing fibers were 65 weight percent E-glass and the matrix was an amorphous rigid polyurethane. The result of tensile testing clearly revealed the detrimental effect of water exposure on the tensile properties of the composite. The tensile strength of the specimens decreased by about 51% after being exposed to salt water or distilled water environment at 373 K (100°C) for 750 hours. Lower temperature exposures showed lower degradation. Investigation on the stress-corrosion behavior of the composite in salt water revealed that the pre-stressed material failed immediately after exposure to a 373 K (100°C) solution. At lower temperatures the failure was observed at longer exposure times.

INTRODUCTION

The use of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) for structural applications is a widely growing field. These materials provide a light weight and low cost alternative to conventional materials. As the world's land and shallow depth off-shore oil reserves are being depleted, there will be the need to drill for oil at greater depths. Economic oil recovery at depths of 9000 meters or more will require new lightweight designs and new material systems with high specific stiffness and specific strength [1]. Many applications are being developed in this field which utilize fiber reinforced polymers. Some of these applications include tubing tailored for bending, tension, and pressure, large-diameter tethers, risers, mooring rope, tubing having a low coefficient of thermal expansion and drill pipe for horizontal and extended reach wells. Although the strength of these materials can be readily obtained, the environment's effect on these materials needs to be addressed [2]. These applications require that a material will retain its mechanical properties throughout the expected life of the product, often while submerged continuously in sea water at elevated pressures and temperatures.

For many applications, a thermoplastic composite must perform over a wide temperature range. The mechanical performance of these thermoplastics, including tensile strength and modulus, chemical resistance, and even electrical properties are temperature dependent. Thus, the design engineer must consider temperature as one of the important design parameters in addition to low cost manufacturing process.

The degradation of the mechanical and physical properties of the composite can be caused by fiber, matrix, or fiber/matrix interface breakdown. Physical and chemical degradation of the polymeric matrix can be caused by chemical alteration due to UV exposure or chemical attack,

loss of modulus due to increased temperature, and volumetric expansion due to moisture absorption. As no polymer is totally impermeable to aqueous corrosive chemicals, the resistance of each new material for uses in these environments must be investigated before they can be relied on for structural applications.

Typical reinforcing fibers under investigation include standard modulus carbon fibers, glass, and aramid fibers. Although glass fibers offer corrosion resistance at a competitive price, glass is not totally inert in chemically corrosive environments [3]. As all polymeric matrices will absorb some water after an extended period of time, these environments must be simulated to determine the extent of the degradation the water has on the fibers and interface.

The strength of fiber reinforced polymer depends on the strength of the fibers as well as the ability of the matrix to transfer the applied load to them. Therefore, if the strength of the fiber-matrix interface is reduced, the composite will fail at a lower level of stress. Water penetration into the composite occurs by diffusion through the resin as well as through cracks and voids in the matrix [3]. When water comes into contact with glass fibers, the molecules penetrate into microcracks which are present on the surface of the glass. This causes the cracks to propagate, which makes the fibers much more brittle and prone to failure. Loss of adhesion or debonding at the fiber-matrix interface will accelerate the degradation process of fibers due to water contact [1,3-5]. Stress concentrations may also develop which will cause a loss in fiber strength. Reduction in glass fiber strength and modulus can be accelerated by static fatigue. As a result, loading conditions can act simultaneously causing composite to deteriorate at an increased rate. The combination of thermal and water absorption stresses can cause microcracks in the matrix, which accelerate the absorption and degradation process.

The effect of elevated temperature, ultraviolet rays, and corrosive fluids on the fibers and the matrix is not well defined. Furthermore, different groups of polymers or different molecular configurations of one polymer will yield a diverse set of corrosion resistance characteristics. It has been established that ultraviolet light has a discoloration effect on polyurethane resins after prolonged exposure. This gives the impression that the material has been physically degraded, even if that is not the case. Additives can be used to slow the degradation process, however, each polyurethane formulation variation must be tested separately to determine its resistance accurately.

A new generation of lower cost advanced thermoplastic composites has emerged through the use of engineering grade thermoplastic matrixes [6]. These new materials include resins such as, polyamides, polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyphenylene sulfide (PPS), polypropylene (PP), and polyurethane (PU), which are typically reinforced with glass or carbon fibers. They offer the same benefits as aerospace/defense thermoplastics but are not cost prohibitive.

In this study a thermoplastic product comprising of a polyurethane matrix (4,4'-diphenyl methane diisocyanate monomers and chain extender of cyclohexane dimethanol) and glass fibers (65 % by wt.), known as Fiberod^{®1} is investigated. This thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) was selected for its processing ability, high glass transition temperature of 415 K (142°C), excellent corrosion, fatigue and creep resistance, dimensional stability, and impact properties. This TPU is unique because it is an amorphous polymer with properties associated with crystalline systems. This product is a fully impregnated and consolidated thermoplastic material produced economically by hot melt impregnation. In this process, continuous filaments are pulled through a molten resin bath consisting of a thermoplastic resin. Typical fiber weight percentages range from 40 to 65 percent. The unique feature of this process is the ability to encapsulate or "wetout" the individual reinforcing fibers with the thermoplastic resin.

¹ Fiberod[®] is a registered trademark of Polymer Composites, Inc.

ENVIRONMENTAL TESTING PROCEDURE

The environmental testing procedure was designed to evaluate the effects of ultraviolet light/water condensation, distilled water and salt water, and the interactions between these environmental conditions. It was also designed to determine the effects of bending stress on the material. The samples were made with an average width of 12.5 mm, thickness of 1.0 mm, and of length of 230 mm.

To evaluate the effects of ultraviolet light and water condensation, the specimens were placed in QUVTM Accelerated Weathering Tester equipped with UV-A lamps. The condensation cycle keeps the testing chamber at 100% relative humidity. The UV and condensation cycles were held at a constant temperature of 323 K (50°C), and cycled in 4 hour intervals. Samples were held in place using aluminum fixtures.

To evaluate the effects of a marine environment, samples were placed in a simulated sea water environment. This simulated sea water consists of 24.5 g NaCl and 4.1 g of Na₂SO₄ per liter of distilled water. Specimens were exposed to both distilled water and saltwater at temperatures of 298 K (25°C), 323 K (50°C), and 373 K (100°C). Exposure at the lower two levels was obtained at atmospheric pressure in high density polyethylene containers. At the 373 K the experiments were performed at 2 atm, in an aluminum pressure vessel.

The effect of bending stress on the material was evaluated in the sea water environment as well as in the QUV environment. To do this, samples were bend to a radius of curvature of 24.5 mm, using aluminum fixtures. Both ends of the 230 mm samples were held parallel at a distance of 40 mm from each other. This resulted in a bending stress of approximately 85% of the ultimate tensile strength. Interaction effects between bending stress, water, salt, ultraviolet light and condensation were also evaluated. This was achieved through sequential exposure, with UV and condensation exposure taking place first in all cases.

Exposure levels of 100, 190, 380, 750, 1500, and 2300 hours were used. Seven samples at each exposure level were removed and tested according to ASTM Standard D 3039 - 76: Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Fiber Resin Composites. A gauge length of 127 mm was used. Tabs were fabricated from panels made from the test material. The tabs used were 12.7 x 2.0 x 50.8 mm. Samples were cured at 344 K (71°C) for 2.5 hours. A period of three days was allowed between elevated cure and tensile testing to assure a complete cure.

RESULTS

It can be seen from Fig. 1 that exposure to salt water at 373 K (100°C) has an immediate degrading effect on the tensile strength of fiberglass reinforced polyurethane. The tensile strength was reduced to 51% of the ultimate tensile stress (UTS) after 750 hours of exposure. The effect of UV and condensation is also shown in Fig. 1. After exposure for 2300 hours, a 12% reduction in tensile strength was observed. Figure 1 also demonstrates the variation of tensile strength of specimens subjected to bending stress while in the UV chamber. These samples showed fiber debonding and separation from the matrix after exposure for 2300 hours. These samples did not fail at a significantly lower tensile stress than those which were not subjected to bending stress. Specimens which were exposed to salt water at 298 K (25°C) showed a 12% reduction in tensile strength after a period of 1500 hours and reduction of about 14% after 2300 hours. Also shown in Fig. 1 is the tensile strength of samples exposed to bending stress at 298 K (25°C). Some of these specimens failed (broke into two pieces) during exposure due to bending stress alone, as shown in Fig. 2. At exposure levels of 380, 750, 1500, and 3000 hours, 7, 18, 29, and 40% of the specimens failed in this manner, respectively.

Fig. 1 Average tensile stress at failure as a function of hours of exposure.

Those which did not fail during exposure showed no significant additional decrease in tensile strength over those which were not subjected to bending stress. When specimens loaded in this fashion were placed in salt water at 323 K (50°C), all specimens failed within 24 hours. At 373 K (100°C), all specimens failed in a matter of minutes. The interaction effects between UV and condensation, bending stress, and sea water at 373 K (100°C) are also shown in Fig. 1. These interaction effects were found to be negligible at this temperature, aside from the discoloration resulting from the UV exposure.

Fig. 2 Number of specimens failed in bending stress as a function of hours of exposure to salt water at 298 K.

DISCUSSION

In spite of the numerous research reports [1,3-5] on the tensile failure of fiberglass reinforced composites (FRP) after exposure to water, there is not much information regarding the bending stresses and related failures of these materials. Bending stresses are quite common in many structural members such as beams frames, etc. The present study indicates that there is a tendency for the material to fail at lower strength values under the conditions of static bending as the FRP is exposed to aqueous solutions (stress corrosion). The bending stress creates compressive and tensile stresses on the cross section and shear forces along the length of the bent ribbon.

The results of the bending stress corrosion study show that the specimens failed immediately after exposure to 373 K (100°C) water or saltwater solution when the loading was applied to create a maximum material strain of 2.1% (approximately at 85% of the ultimate tensile strength). Microstructural analysis of the fractured surfaces of the test coupons reveals that there are two distinct failure regions, a compression and tension side (Fig. 3). The tension side showed fiber pullout and matrix deformation (Fig. 4). The compression side showed brittle fiber failure with little or no fiber pullout as expected (Fig. 5). This immediate failure is believed to have been caused by the combination of bending stresses, and the thermal stresses developed as the material was immersed in the hot water. The area under the tensile stress and the area under compressive stress were roughly equal to each other, as would be predicted by mechanics calculations.

Fig. 3 Fractured surface of a polyurethane-fiberglass composite failed by stress-corrosion process at 373 K (100°C).

Fig. 4 Magnified image of an area located on the upper part (tensile region) of the fractured surface illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 5 Magnified image of an area located on the lower part (compression region) of the fractured surface illustrated in Fig. 3.

The results of the investigation on the stress corrosion behavior of the FRP specimens exposed to saltwater solution at 298 K (25°C) reveal that these samples failed after a longer time (Fig. 1) The fracture surfaces of these samples were also studied under the SEM (Fig. 6). The failure mode for the samples was found to be different from those that failed at a higher temperature. The failure of the fracture surface was found to be in tensile mode only, with fiber pullout and a rough surface. This is because water penetration into the composite occurs by diffusion through

the resin as well as through cracks and voids in the matrix [5]. This indicates that the failure of glass reinforced polymers is caused by the eventual seepage of the water to the fibers. There was an increased amount of cracks in the matrix on the tensile side of the specimens caused by the bending loading. This provided a path of less resistance for the water to penetrate and degrade the glass fibers compared to the compression side which has more resistance toward water permeation. As more fibers failed due to the water exposure in the tension region, additional glass fibers were exposed resulting in propagation of the tensile failure.

Fig. 6 Fractured surface of a polyurethane-fiberglass composite failed by stress-corrosion process at 298 K (25°C).

Those specimens which did not fail under bending stress were tested under tensile load. These samples did not fail at a significantly lower stress than those subjected to the same exposure level without bending stress. This result indicates that the bending stress failure of specimens had been initiated with minor matrix defects.

The exposure of glass reinforced polyurethane to sea water with no applied stresses at 373 K (100°C) showed a reduction in tensile strength to 51% of the original value after 750 hours of exposure. This result agrees with the result of investigation on the degradation of the same material in a salt water and corrosive gas environment [7]. Expectedly, the degradation resulting from exposure to sea water was slower at lower temperatures. As stated in the results section, tensile specimens subjected to salt water exposure at 298 K (25°C) showed a decrease in tensile strength. Specimens exposed for 2300 hours were reduced to 86% of their original tensile strength.

The most noticeable effect of exposing the glass reinforced polyurethane samples to ultraviolet light and water condensation was the gradual discoloration of the matrix. As received material was light tan in appearance, this color darkened as exposure levels increased. Much work has been done in the area of polyurethane discoloration in the presence of UV light. Although discoloration began immediately, only a 12% reduction in tensile strength occurred after 2300 hours of exposure. The effect of this degradation on specimens subjected to bending stress caused glass fiber delamination, as seen in the samples which were exposed for 2300 hours.

CONCLUSIONS

The result of investigation on the performance of a unidirectional fiberglass reinforced polyurethane composite revealed that the tensile strength of the specimens decreased by about 51% after being exposed to salt water or distilled water environment at 373 K for 750 hours. At lower temperatures exposures showed lower degradation rates. Investigation on the stress-corrosion behavior of the composite in salt water revealed that the pre-stressed material failed immediately after exposure to a 373 K solution. At lower temperatures the failure was observed at longer exposure times. Microstructural analysis of the fractured surface of specimens which failed under stress corrosion (bending stress) at 373 K showed two distinct failure regions, compression and tension, while the samples failed at 298 K after longer exposure time showed only tensile fracture mode. Continuous glass reinforced composites suffer from a breakdown of fiber-matrix adhesion. They should be used with caution in sea water at elevated temperature, specially if glass composite is highly loaded.

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